

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF EUDALENE.

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A new synthesis of eudalene has been effected starting from sodium salt of ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate.

Eudalene, obtained by selenium dehydrogenation of selenene and eudesmol, has been shown to be 1-methyl-7-isopropyl-naphthalene and has been synthesised (*cf.* Ruzicka and Stoll, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 15, 925; Darzen and Levy, *Compt. rend.*, 1932, 194, 2056; Barnett and Sanders, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 435).

Since dicyclic sesquiterpenes are derivatives of hydrogenated naphthalenes, it was thought desirable to synthesise hydrogenated naphthalenes which will ultimately lead to the synthesis of eudalene. The following scheme describes a new synthesis of eudalene starting from cyclohexanone derivative.

Sodium salt of ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (I, R=H) is allowed to react with ethyl β -chloropropionate and the resulting diethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate (I, R=CH₂CH₂CO₂Et) is hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid to yield 6-methylcyclohexanone-2- β -propionic acid (II). Ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2- β -propionate, obtained on esterification, reacts with bromoacetic ester in presence of zinc according to Reformatsky to give a mixture of diethyl 6-methylcyclohexane-1-ol-1-acetate-2- β -propionate (III) and the corresponding unsaturated ester. The crude mixture, on dehydration with thionyl chloride and pyridine in ether solution, gives a pure sample of the unsaturated ester which is then reduced in alcoholic solution by means of hydrogen in presence of platinum oxide catalyst to diethyl 6-methylcyclohexane-1-acetate-2- β -propionate (IV). The latter compound is then treated in benzene solution with molecularised sodium to yield ethyl 2-keto-8-methyldecalene-1-carboxylate (V, R=H; R=CO₂Et). On hydrolysing the above ester, 8-methyl- β -decalone (V, R=R'=H) is obtained. This when treated with isopropyl magnesium iodide according to Grignard gives a carbinol and the corresponding unsaturated compound. The mixture on selenium dehydrogenation gives eudalene (VI) identified through its picrate.

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl 6-Methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (I, R=H).—A cooled mixture of 2-methylcyclohexanone (200 g.) and ethyl oxalate (300 g.) was poured to a cold alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (from 40 g. sodium and 650 c.c. alcohol). The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at a cool place and then decomposed by adding cold water strongly acidulated with hydrochloric acid. The ester was precipitated as a thick oil and extracted with ether. The ether extract was dried (sodium sulphate), the ether removed and the residual oil heated in vacuum. Between 95° and 100° evolution of carbon monoxide takes place. It was then heated to 180-200° in an oil-bath until the evolution of carbon monoxide was complete (about 4 hours). It was then distilled in vacuum at 97°/4 mm.

Diethyl 6-Methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-propionate (I, R=CH₂·CH₂·CO₂Et).—(a) Finely divided metallic sodium (7.7 g.) in dry benzene (250 c.c.) was slowly treated with ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (60 g.) and the mixture kept overnight. Ethyl β-chloropropionate (48 g.) was then added and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 6 hours. It was cooled, washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and the benzene removed. The residual oil distilled at 158-65°/2.5 mm., yield 69 g.

(b) Ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (20 g.) was added to the solution of sodium (2.6 g.) in alcohol (31 c.c.) and the solid sodium salt

was heated under reflux for 6 hours with ethyl β -chloropropionate (18 g.). After dilution the condensation product was extracted with ether, the ether removed and the product distilled at $158-65^{\circ}/2.5$ mm., yield 21 g.

(c) A solution of sodium ethoxide from sodium (2.6 g.) in alcohol (70 c.c.) was slowly added with shaking to a mixture of ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (20 g.) and ethyl β -chloropropionate (16 g.), absolute alcohol (50 c.c.) and sodium iodide (0.3 g.) with cooling in a bath of ice-cold water. The reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 2 hours. After refluxing for further 2 hours, the greater part of alcohol was evaporated. The residue was poured into ice-water (1 litre) and the precipitated oil isolated by means of ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. It was then distilled at $158-65^{\circ}/2.5$ mm., yield 10 g. (Found: C, 63.56; H, 8.26. $C_{15}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 63.4; H, 8.4 per cent).

6-Methylcyclohexanone-2- β -propionic Acid (II).—The foregoing ester (30 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with concentrated hydrochloric acid (180 c.c.) by boiling for 3-4 hours and the liquid was concentrated to a small bulk under reduced pressure and diluted with a saturated solution of ammonium sulphate. An oil then separated which was extracted with ether. The extract was dried (sodium sulphate) and evaporated. The acid was then distilled in vacuum, b.p. $165-70^{\circ}/4$ mm., which solidified on keeping in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, m.p. 71° , yield 100 g. from 120 g. of ester. (Found: C, 64.8; H, 9.0. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7 per cent).

Ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2- β -propionate was obtained by esterifying 6-methylcyclohexanone-2- β -propionic acid (70 g.) with absolute alcohol (240 c.c.) saturated with hydrochloric acid at 0° . The vessel was kept overnight at ordinary temperature. The solution was then refluxed for 4 hours. It was then cooled, treated with water and extracted with ether. Ether solution was washed with dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate, dried over calcium chloride, the ether removed and the residue distilled at $135^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 60 g. (Found: C, 67.7; H, 9.14. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 67.9; H, 9.4 per cent).

Diethyl 6-Methylcyclohexan-1-ol-1-acetate-2- β -propionate (III).—A mixture of ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-2- β -propionate (40 g.), bromoacetic ester (31.5 g.) and zinc wool (12.3 g.) was covered with dry benzene (150 c.c.). A crystal of iodine was added as a catalyst. On warming the mixture the reaction started and the mixture was heated for 3 hours. The solution was then decomposed with ice and sulphuric acid. Excess of zinc was filtered off and the benzene solution was washed thoroughly with ice-cold sodium carbonate

solution followed by water. After drying with calcium chloride, benzene was removed and fractionation of the residual oil gave hydroxy ester (small quantity), b.p. $167^{\circ}/3$ mm. The portion boiling below this temperature seemed to be a mixture of the hydroxy ester and the unsaturated ester. A fraction boiling at $153^{\circ}/3$ mm. gave analytical results in agreement with those of an unsaturated ester, yield 20 g. [Found (unsaturated ester) : C, 68.1; H, 8.7. $C_{16}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 68.0; H, 9.2 per cent].

Dimethyl 6-Methylcyclohexylidene-1-acetate-2- β -propionate.—The crude hydroxy ester (82 g.) was mixed with dry pyridine (52.2 g.) and the mixture was diluted with dry ether (500 c.c.). The solution was cooled in ice and salt and thionyl chloride (34.4 g.) was added drop by drop with constant shaking. After the addition was complete, the mixture was kept at room temperature and after 2 hours, it was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was thoroughly washed with acid and alkali. The crude solution left after evaporation of ether was diluted with benzene (300 c.c.) and heated on the water-bath with precipitated copper (5 g.) to remove sulphur. The insoluble residue was filtered, the solvent removed, and the pure oil distilled in vacuum, b.p. $153^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 50 g. (Found : C, 68.4 H, 9.6. $C_{16}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 68.0; H, 9.2 per cent).

Diethyl 6-Methylcyclohexane-1-acetate-2- β -propionate (IV).—The unsaturated ester (50 g.) was slowly reduced in alcoholic solution (150 c.c.) by means of hydrogen, a platinum oxide catalyst (0.5 g.) being used. The product after working up in the usual manner boiled at $149^{\circ}/3$ mm. It did not decolourise a solution of potassium permanganate. (Found : C, 67.8; H, 9.3. $C_{16}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 67.6; H, 9.8 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Keto-8-methyldecalene-3-carboxylate (V, R=H: R'=CO₂Et or V, R=CO₂Et; R'=H).—The foregoing ester (10 g.) and molecular sodium (1.7 g.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath. The heating was discontinued when the reaction became vigorous and the mixture further heated for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried and evaporated. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a pale yellow oil, b.p. $150^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 5 g. (Found : C, 70.4; H, 9.3. $C_{14}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 9.2 per cent).

8-Methyl- β -decalone (V, R=R'=H).—The keto-ester was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours, and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried (sodium sulphate). After

removing ether it was distilled at 101-104°/3 mm. (Found : C, 79·8; H, 10·9. $C_{11}H_{10}O$ requires C, 7·5; H, 10·8 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 177°. (Found : N, 19·3. $C_{12}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 18·8 per cent).

Eudalene (VI).—To an ethereal solution of *isopropyl* magnesium iodide (3 g., of *isopropyl* iodide, 0·8 g. of magnesium) was added with cooling the above ketone (3 g.) in ether. After standing for 12 hours at the ordinary temperature it was refluxed for 2 hours. The product was decomposed with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was extracted with ether and the extract washed with water, dried and evaporated.

The above mixture was distilled, and the distillate mixed with three times its weight of selenium and heated for 30 hours at 300-320°. After cooling, the whole mass was repeatedly extracted with ether and on removal of the solvent it was distilled in vacuum. The distillate was again distilled over sodium when a clear mobile liquid was obtained having a characteristic, aromatic smell.

The picrate of the hydrocarbon, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 92° (lit. 90-91°). (Found : N, 10·3. $C_{20}H_{10}O_7N$ requires N, 10·17 per cent).

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